

Primary Ovarian Insufficiency and Fertility Preservation: A Case Report with Clinical Insights

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ABSTRACT

Background: Primary ovarian insufficiency (POI) refers to the loss of ovarian function before the age of 40. A comprehensive approach involving diagnosis and joint management is essential to determine the most suitable strategy, whether for fertility preservation or planning for egg donation.

Objective: To present a case report of patients with primary ovarian insufficiency in southeastern Mexico.

Materials and Methods: Retrospective study, case report.

Intervention: None; data obtained from clinical records.

Results: Description of four cases of primary ovarian insufficiency with fertility desire, individualized management approach, and subsequent protocols for egg donation or embryo adoption.

Conclusion: Timely diagnosis is crucial to establish the best reproductive prognosis. In this study, we present four cases of POI referred to the outpatient clinic at the Reproductive Medicine Department, Agustín O'Horán General Hospital, Mérida, Yucatán, Mexico. All patients met diagnostic criteria and were treated with tailored approaches adapted to their individual reproductive goals.

KEYWORDS: premature ovarian failure, in vitro fertilization, prevalence, donor oocyte, fertility preservation

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BACKGROUND

Primary ovarian insufficiency (POI) is defined as the loss of ovarian function before the age of 40.[1,2] The reported prevalence is 1% in the general population before age 40, and 0.1% before age 30.[3] A comprehensive approach is required to manage long-term complications.[1]

Fertility and the ability to have children are crucial components of quality of life for many women.[4] POI is

associated with significant emotional burden due to infertility or subfertility, intermittent ovarian function, vasomotor symptoms, bone loss, cardiovascular risk, and sexual dysfunction.[4,5] The functional consequences of POI on ovarian activity and systemic health are illustrated in *Figure 1*.

A graphical representation of systemic and reproductive consequences of POI.

Figure 1 Impact of Primary Ovarian Insufficiency on Ovary Function

Residual ovarian function varies among POI patients. Those with spontaneous ovulation often experience infrequent ovulation, resulting in prolonged time to conception compared to women with normal ovarian reserve. Most require fertility treatments.[4] Women at risk due to genetic predisposition, medical conditions, or gonadotoxic cancer treatments may benefit from fertility preservation strategies.[4]

In vitro fertilization (IVF) using autologous oocytes may be viable when residual ovarian reserve allows for stimulation. However, outcomes are generally poor due to diminished reserve, requiring high doses of exogenous gonadotropins and often yielding four or fewer follicles. This results in limited oocyte retrieval and few or no embryos available for transfer or cryopreservation.[4]

Multiple IVF cycles may be necessary to achieve conception. Contributing factors to IVF failure include low ovarian reserve, advanced maternal age, suboptimal endometrial environment, and procedural complications. Age is the most significant predictor of live birth rates.[7,9]

Women with undetectable anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH)—a critical marker of ovarian reserve—and clinical hypoestrogenism benefit from IVF with donor oocytes. This approach is also promising for those with genetically-linked POI wishing to avoid passing on heritable conditions. Embryo transfer success rates range from 50–60%, with live birth outcomes per attempt.[4,10]

Donor age directly correlates with success. With the increasing availability of cryopreserved embryos, anonymous

embryo donation through embryo banks offers additional options. Women with POI and no male partner may benefit from donor embryos. Donor oocyte or embryo use is increasingly relevant as more young women undergo gonadotoxic cancer therapies.[4,11]

Endometrial preparation is also key. Letru-Konirsch et al. reported 30–50% pregnancy rates using fresh embryos and 15–25% with thawed embryos, following optimal estradiol and progesterone regimens.[8,12]

Additionally, psychological counseling and emotional support are vital components in the multidisciplinary care of women with POI, as these patients frequently experience emotional distress and anxiety related to infertility and early menopause.[13,14]

Emerging technologies, such as ovarian tissue cryopreservation and in vitro activation (IVA), have been proposed as alternative fertility preservation methods in selected POI patients with residual follicles, although their clinical application is still limited.[15,16]

Genetic testing, including next-generation sequencing (NGS), is being increasingly used to identify mutations associated with POI, offering insights into pathophysiology and facilitating counseling for affected individuals and their families.[17,18]

IVF and cryopreservation of oocytes/embryos are well-established with favorable outcomes.[5,19]

OBJECTIVE

To present a case report of patients with primary ovarian insufficiency in southeastern Mexico.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Retrospective study, case report. Description of 4 patients with primary ovarian insufficiency, through clinical record review. Variables included: age, gravidity, body mass index (BMI), anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) values, and individualized protocols.

INTERVENTION

None; information was obtained from the clinical record.

RESULTS

PATIENT 1: A 27-year-old woman, gravida 0, body mass index (BMI) 21, presenting with secondary amenorrhea for 6 months and expressing a desire for pregnancy. Anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) was 0.1 ng/ml. Genetic testing for fragile X syndrome was negative. Antral follicle count showed 2 follicles measuring 10 mm. The patient wished to attempt oocyte cryopreservation and started a Step Down protocol with recombinant FSH (rFSH) at a dose of 187 IU/day. At follicular aspiration, no oocytes were retrieved. The patient proceeded to an oocyte donation protocol.

PATIENT 2: A 31-year-old woman, gravida 0, BMI 27, presenting for fertility treatment. Antral follicle count was decreased, with 3 follicles in the right ovary and 1 follicle in the left ovary measuring 10 mm. AMH was 0.3 ng/ml. She underwent an oocyte banking protocol. In the first cycle, rFSH 225 IU/day was administered, resulting in the aspiration of 2 metaphase II (MII) oocytes. The second cycle used rFSH

150 IU/day, yielding 2 MII oocytes. The third cycle combined an aromatase inhibitor (5 mg/day) plus rFSH 150 IU/day, resulting in 3 MII oocytes. The patient opted for oocyte donation.

PATIENT 3: A 32-year-old woman, gravida 1, one cesarean delivery, BMI 26, seeking fertility treatment. Antral follicle count showed 4 follicles in the right ovary and 2 in the left ovary. AMH was 0.3 ng/ml. IVF was initiated using a Step Down protocol with rFSH 300 IU/day tapering to 150 IU/day. Follicular aspiration retrieved 4 MII oocytes. Two blastocysts were biopsied for preimplantation genetic testing for aneuploidy (PGT-A), graded 2BC and 2AA, with reported aneuploidies of trisomy 21 and 46XY +8. The patient expressed interest in oocyte donation.

PATIENT 4: A 34-year-old woman, gravida 0, BMI 23, with desire for pregnancy. AMH was 0.3 ng/ml. She had a severe male factor (oligoasthenoteratozoospermia - OAT). An oocyte banking protocol for IVF/ICSI was initiated. The first cycle used combined rFSH/LH (150/75 IU/day) with aspiration of 2 MII oocytes. The second cycle used the same doses, with aspiration of 1 MII oocyte. The third and fourth cycles included an aromatase inhibitor (5 mg/day) plus rFSH 150 IU/day, with aspirations yielding 2 and 1 MII oocytes respectively. Two blastocysts underwent PGT-A; the first showed 45XX-18 and the second was chaotic. Embryo adoption was planned.

The main clinical characteristics and ovarian response of the four patients are summarized in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Characteristics of the Four Cases of Primary Ovarian Insufficiency

Summarizes age, BMI, AMH levels, stimulation protocol, and oocyte retrieval.

Table 1. Characteristics of the Four Cases of Primary Ovarian Insufficiency

Patient	Age (years)	Pregnancy Attempts	AMH (ng/mL)	Antral Follicular Count	Treatment Cycles	Outcome
Patient 1	27	Desire pregnancy	0.1	2 oocytes (right)	1 cycle no oocytes	Plan for egg donation
Patient 2	31	Desire pregnancy	0.3	4 oocytes (right-1 left)	3 cycles 2 oocytes 3 third cycl	Plan for egg donation
Patient 3	32	Desire pregnancy	0.3	4 oocytes (right-2 left)	1 cycle	Plan for egg donation
Patient 4	34	Desire pregnancy	0.3	4 oocytes (severe male)	4 cycles 2 oocytes 1 oocytes	Plan for embryo adoption

A comparative view of stimulation protocols and oocyte retrieval is shown in *Figure 2*.

Controlled Ovarian Stimulation Attempts and Oocyte Retrieval Results in POI Patients

Figure 2. Controlled Ovarian Stimulation Attempts and Oocyte Retrieval Results in POI Patients

CONCLUSION

A diagnosis of primary ovarian insufficiency has a significant impact on both the physical and emotional health of affected patients. Women may experience depression, anxiety, and other disorders closely related to the uncertainty of their reproductive prognosis.

It is essential to advise women who prioritize fertility to seek assisted conception through in vitro fertilization with donor oocytes or embryos.[7]

DISCUSSION

Observational studies report a cumulative live birth rate of 86.1% after four oocyte donation cycles in POI patients.[7] Identifying the etiology of POI remains a challenge; approximately 65% are idiopathic, with some linked to autoimmune conditions—thyroid autoimmunity being the most common.[7]

Pathophysiological mechanisms are still under investigation. Most cases remain underdiagnosed. Fertility consultations typically occur later in reproductive life due to delayed

conception. Expanded access to fertility services, including early referral to reproductive specialists, has been shown to improve outcomes in women with POI.[20]

Fertility prognosis and bone density evaluation—often compromised by estrogen deficiency—are key components of comprehensive POI management.[7]

This case series highlights individualized treatment strategies, emphasizing tailored approaches and reproductive counseling. The fertility impact of POI necessitates early referral and intervention.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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